

HESANDA – MONASH NODE

Master guidelines. November 2023

Abstract

Health Data Australia (HDA) contains descriptions of health datasets, provided by the data owners and stored elsewhere. To get access to the data, researchers submit a request to the owner, who will review and determine whether access can be granted.

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Health Data Australia

Overview of Health Data Australia

Health Data Australia (HDA) helps researchers discover and access health data. They do not store the data itself but provide descriptions of the data from their data publishing partners. Using HDA, researchers can search these descriptions, find data of use to do their research, then request access to it. The request will be sent to the owner of the data to review. Data owners receive email notifications about new data requests and can then log into the HDA Data Request platform to review the request and determine whether access can be granted and then respond to the researcher requesting access. If the request is approved, the owner arranges for the researcher to be given access to the data.

The dataset descriptions ('metadata') contained on HDA help researchers understand the kinds of data that exist and assess whether a dataset may be of value to their research, without the need to actually access the data. In addition to metadata, data owners provide other documentation describing the data they hold, such as study protocols and data dictionaries.

Using HDA, researchers can search for data, save their searches, submit and manage data requests.

HeSANDAs

The information on Health Data Australia was provided by the HeSANDAs network. HeSANDAs is a network of 72 health research organisations working collaboratively as nine 'nodes' to give researchers better access to health data. For more information about HeSANDAs, see [here](#). Health Data Australia launched in July 2023. Over the next five years, it will be expanded to incorporate a wider array of data collections from different health research studies, as well as government and health service data. [Here](#) is the link to the Platform.

The HeSANDAs Network

There are 9 HeSANDAs nodes that represent 72 health research organisations across Australia

Melbourne Academic Centre for Health (MACH) Clinical Trials Consortium Node <i>Administered by:</i> The University of Melbourne	Queensland Node <i>Administered by:</i> Health Translation Queensland
Mental Health Node <i>Administered by:</i> Deakin University	South Australia Node <i>Administered by:</i> South Australian Health and Medical Research Institute (SAHMRI)
Monash and Partners Node <i>Administered by:</i> Monash University	Sydney Health Partners Node <i>Administered by:</i> NHMRC Clinical Trials Centre at The University of Sydney
National Cancer Cooperative Trials Groups Node <i>Administered by:</i> Australasian Leukaemia and Lymphoma Group (ALLG)	West Australian Node <i>Administered by:</i> Curtin University
Northern Australia Node <i>Administered by:</i> Menzies School of Health Research	

Logos: Monash Partners, MONASH University, Australian Research Data Commons

Figure 1. The HeSANDAs network

How to view a Health Dataset in HeSANDA

Record view page overview

Once you have discovered health datasets of interest, the Health Data Australia (HDA) portal provides a comprehensive overview of each dataset's metadata, providing essential information about the dataset and the access option. You can also save the health dataset to your MyHDA profile page, which gives you quick access to this dataset in the future.

One of the prominent features of the record view page is the ability to examine the dataset's connections to other entities. By navigating through the graph visualisation and the listed related parties, you can get a clear understanding about the origin and sourcing of the health dataset, i.e. the funder and the collector. The related study section provided additional details about the study to which the dataset is related. This information expands the scope of understanding by providing valuable context and background information about the dataset.

The figure below shows an example of a record view page in HDA and the name of different sections on the page

The screenshot shows the record view page for the dataset 'Piloting a Treatment to Address Social Media Use and Eating Disorder Risk in University Students'. The page is divided into several sections, each highlighted with a red dashed border and a numbered callout:

- 1 Title Bar:** The top header area containing the dataset title and the Funder (Flinders University).
- 2 Data Access and Saving Options:** A section with a 'Data Access' button and a 'Save to MyHDA' button.
- 3 Dataset Description:** A text area providing a detailed description of the pilot study, including participant demographics and intervention details.
- 4 Graph Visualisation:** A network graph showing the dataset's connections to other entities, with a vertical 'FILTER' bar on the right.
- 5 Related Parties:** A section listing related people (e.g., Aggregators by Media, Therapy) and related organizations (e.g., Department of Education, Skills and Employment, Australian Government).
- 6 Subjects:** A section listing the dataset's subjects, such as 'FDS: Psychology 1'.
- 7 Identifiers:** A section listing the dataset's identifiers, including a DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.25957/FPVFPY047>.
- 8 Related Study:** A section providing details about the related study, including a 'Brief Summary' of the project's aims and objectives.

Fig 1.1 Record View Page in HDA

Title Bar

The title bar on the record view page presents the most essential information about the health dataset. It includes the dataset's title and the name of its publisher, allowing users to quickly identify and understand the dataset they are reviewing. An icon in the top-right corner specifically indicates the record type.

Data Access and Saving Options

This section provides you with intuitive functionality to interact with your desired datasets. Clicking the button "Access the data" will redirect you to an Express of Interest (EOI) form, in which you can fill in detailed information about yourself and the project you're working on, in order to be granted approval to access the health dataset.

Clicking the button "Save to MyHDA" allows you to save the dataset to MyHDA profile page, so that you can quickly retrieve the dataset for future reference and analysis.

For a more detailed instruction about how to request access to a health dataset, see: [How to Request Access to a Health Dataset](#)

For more information about the saved datasets, see: [MyHDA > My Saved Data Requests](#)

Dataset Description

The Dataset Description section serves as a reference point that provides an overview of the health dataset.

Graph Visualisation

The interactive Graph Visualisation section offers intuitive functionalities for you to explore different connections associated to the health dataset. This powerful feature allows you to uncover relationships with various individuals, organisations, and other health datasets on multiple levels. Different vertices represent different type of entities. The arrows between these vertices indicates the way they are related. You can also double-click any vertex on the graph to see if it's connected with other vertices, so that you can have a more comprehensive view about how data and people/organisations are connected.

For a more detailed instruction about how to use the graph visualisation, see: [Graph Visualisation](#)

Related Parties

This section introduces the individuals and organisations that are related to the current health dataset in text format. For more information about the related parties, see: [Related Parties](#)

Subjects

Each subject in the dataset represents a descriptive element that highlights the primary focus of the health dataset. It aids in the discoverability of datasets and facilitates searching, filtering, and categorisation of datasets that align with your research interests or information requirements. Clicking a subject will redirect you to a search result page displaying all the datasets associated with that subject in their metadata. This allows for convenient exploration and enhances your ability to find relevant and valuable information for your own research needs.

Identifiers

The Identifiers section lists all the available identifiers of the current health dataset and will provide redirection to the identifier if the identifier is resolvable.

Related Study

In HDA, every health dataset is related to a study. This section serves as a valuable resource for understanding the context, background, and additional information related to the dataset's associated study. For more information about the related study, see: [Related Study](#)

Overview of the HDA Data Request Platform – HeSANDA

HDA Data Request is a platform for data owners (or their delegates) to receive and respond to data requests submitted via Health Data Australia. To use the platform, you will need to:

1. Register with HDA
2. Provide metadata about your datasets

Once you are registered with us, a user account will be created for you. The platform uses Jira software to manage requests. All requests are visible in your user dashboard. Your user dashboard is your central view of all the data requests that you've received. These include:

- New requests
- Requests that are in progress and require your action
- Requests that are in progress and awaiting an action from the requestor
- Requests that have been completed or closed.

From your [dashboard](#) you can open any of the requests you've received to view its details and to progress it through the request workflow. You can also download the request as a PDF (e.g. to forward to a chief investigator, data access committee, or anyone else who may need to review the request).

How do I get set up to use HDA Data Request– HeSANDA

What is a Point Of Contact (POC)?

On the HDA Data Request platform, a 'POC' is the person that has been designated by the data owner to receive and respond to data requests submitted to the platform. The POC may be the data owner, the data custodian, or someone they nominate. For the Monash Node – this is Helix, at Monash University. All HDA requests will go to the helix support email which is monitored by several Helix staff (helix@monash.edu).

A POC is responsible for:

- Receiving data requests from the HDA Data Request/ARDC Data Request platform
- Actioning the data request in accordance with the governance arrangements determined by the data owner
- Actively reviewing and tracking the progress of data requests within the HDA Data Request/ARDC Data Request platform
- Responding to data requests in a timely manner.
- Liaising with the data about the progress of their request

(Please note: The POC is an administrative role within the platform and is not intended or designed to replace the governance arrangements or roles determined by the data owner. A data owner may choose to act as a POC, or they may delegate someone to act on their behalf. The details of these arrangements are at the discretion of the data owner. The Monash node has designated Helix as the contact for data requests through HDA)

Account Basics - HeSANDA

How do I register to use HDA Data Request?

Monash POC will register on your behalf. Please contact helix@monash.edu if you have not received this information.

Data Requests in HeSANDA

Overview of the HDA Data Request platform

The HDA Data Request platform allows data owners, custodians, or their delegates to receive and respond to data requests submitted by researchers via Health Data Australia.

The platform uses a standard high-level administrative workflow for tracking and responding to data requests while still allowing data owners to apply their own specific governance requirements for approving access to data.

Overview of the data request process

To make accessing data easier, all datasets listed on HDA adhere to a common framework for responding to data requests.

Figure 1.1 Framework for responding to data requests

Different datasets listed on HDA have different governance and requirements for how access is granted. This information should be included in the listing of each dataset. Some datasets may only be available to certain kinds of researchers or for certain purposes. There may be other conditions for using data such as how it is stored or requirements for collaboration. This information should be included in the listing of each dataset. In most cases, the owner will require a data sharing agreement to be completed before access is granted.

Once a data request is submitted by a researcher, the workflow for responding is as follows:

Figure 1.2 HDA Data Request workflow

The steps in this workflow are designed to be flexible to different situations and governance requirements. The person receiving the data request (the 'point of contact' or 'POC') follows their own governance rules and liaises with the chief investigator, data access committee, or any other person responsible for reviewing the data request.

The POC uses the platform to record the progress of the request, ask the requestor for additional information or modifications to the request, and to record the final outcome. The requestor can use the platform to respond to the POC's enquiries, and can also withdraw the request if required.

If the request is approved, the data owner and requestor will liaise directly to complete a data sharing agreement (if required) and to organise access to the data. These final steps occur outside the platform, but their outcome is recorded in the platform for future reference.

Workflow and statuses:

As shown in the diagram above, there are different pathways through the workflow that a POC can choose depending on the specific request and progress of the review process. As the request progresses, the POC has control and responsibility for updating the status within HDA Data Request (NB. the only exception is the 'Withdrawn' status - see below for details). An explanation of each status is as follows:

- Submitted - This status is automatically assigned by the platform when a data request is first submitted by a Requestor
- Review in progress - This status is manually assigned by the POC. It should be used to indicate that the review of a new (or modified) data request is underway.
- Modifications requested - This status is manually assigned by the POC. It should be used to indicate that the Requestor has been asked to modify and re-submit their request.
- In-principle approval - This status is manually assigned by the POC. It should be used to indicate that the data owner (or their delegate) supports the proposed use of their data. This status should be assigned prior to a data sharing agreement being signed, or the data being released. It is at this stage that the data owner (or their delegate) should liaise directly with the Requestor to arrange the signing of agreements and providing access to the data.
- Denied - This status is manually assigned by the POC. It should be used to indicate that the request was not supported by the data owner (or their delegate).
- Discontinued - This status is manually assigned by the POC. There are 2 scenarios when it should be used:
 - If the POC and Requestor agree to discontinue a data request that is currently in progress (NB. A Requestor can withdraw their data request, but only if the review has not yet begun, or if the POC requests modifications. The 'Discontinued' status can only be assigned by the POC to indicate the outcome of the request, and to distinguish that outcome from the 'Denied' status which is used to record that the request was rejected by the data owner (or their delegate)).
 - If a request has received in-principle approval but is then discontinued and access to the data is not granted. This may occur if the data owner and requestor can't agree to the terms of the data sharing agreement, and the request is discontinued at the stage of signing the agreement.
- Data released - This status is manually assigned by the POC. It should be used to indicate that (if applicable) a data sharing agreement has been signed and that the Requestor has now been given access to the data.
- Withdrawn - This status is manually assigned by the Requestor. There are 2 scenarios when it can be used:
 - Before the review process begins, the Requestor may withdraw requests that have been submitted. E.g. If they submitted a draft version of the request in error.
 - If the POC has requested modifications to the data request that the Requestor is not willing or able to make, then they may withdraw the request.

Please note:

- The Requestor (and Watcher, if one is assigned) will be automatically notified of all updates to the status of the data request
- The POC (and Watcher, if one is assigned) will be automatically notified when a data request is submitted, or if the Requestor updates the status to 'Withdrawn'